

Table S5. Multivariate mixed-effects logistic regression for low birth weight in *P. falciparum* positive women at delivery

Odds ratios (OR) with 95% CI and *p* values are presented of univariate models (*p* values <0.05 in bold).

<i>dhfr</i> Fixed effect(s)	LBW			
	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>
Triple <i>dhfr</i> mutation	1.13	0.40	3.15	0.818
Age (10 years)	1.17	0.99	1.38	0.066
Gravidity	0.45	0.24	0.83	0.010
Season#	1.38	0.29	6.53	0.687
IPTp-SP doses	0.40	0.20	0.79	0.008
AL	0.75	0.40	1.40	0.367

AL = artemether-lumefantrine therapy; LBW = low birth weight; # low transmission season = 0, high transmission season = 1;